



Stickers for your snowboard are cool. Free stickers in the mail are even cooler. Stickers are a must-have, but not everyone wants to spend money on them. How can you get stickers free of charge for [look at this](#) your snowboard? There are several easy and really easy options to get this done.

It is easiest to have someone just give you a sticker. This isn't going to happen unless you are walking around a snowboard event like the US Open or the X-Games. Vendors at these events are hungry for people to take their stickers so they give them to anyone who asks or is walking by their booth.

The other option is to get lucky when you buy a product. Often when you buy snowboard equipment, the company, if they are smart, will send a few stickers with the order. This doesn't always happen however and some products you don't even buy online so they don't ship them so you don't get the stickers you want. You can think of energy drinks such as Monster or Rock Star. They have some of the most beautiful stickers. I was never offered a sticker for buying a Monster energy drink from my Quickie Mart.

Another option is to ask for stickers at a Zumiez-certified retailer. They usually have a ton just sitting around taking up space so they might as well be on your board.

The problem remains however. What can I do to get stickers free of charge?

The easiest way that requires the least amount of effort that I know of is to contact the companies directly. It is totally free and can even be done while you sit on your couch and watch Robot Chicken reruns too. You have the option to call, write, or fill out their contact form online. You can pick and choose which companies to contact which requires you to hunt down email addresses and sort through all of the website mumbo-jumbo to find the snail mail info or contact form. It is best to search for a forum or website that already has this information. Then you just pick and choose which company to contact for your free stickers.

This is not a perfect system because not all companies will send you the stickers for free but a lot of them will. The companies that don't want stickers will ask you to send them a stamped, self-addressed envelope. They won't need to pay for postage and you'll receive your stickers. Others actually want you to send cash; usually a dollar or two. You can decide how much effort and time you want to put into getting your stickers. However, a few stickers sent in the mail is well worth it.